

Assessing the Role of School Libraries in Supporting Information Needs of Higher Secondary Students in Tatibandh, Raipur District

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Abstract

The present study assesses the effectiveness of school libraries in fulfilling the information needs of students at the upper secondary education level in Tatibandh, Raipur District. The present research used a mixed-methods approach to examine the current state, perceived effectiveness, and challenges encountered by school libraries in meeting the diverse information requirements of students. The poll reveals that while libraries are widely recognised as crucial academic resources, with 75% of students considering them indispensable for their studies, there are significant disparities in the quality and accessibility of services across universities. The key findings reveal a shortage of skilled librarians (only 60% of schools hire full-time professionals), limited availability of digital resources (30% offer access to online databases), and varying degrees of effectiveness in meeting different information needs (70% satisfaction for curriculum support, but only 45-50% for current events and career guidance). The research underscores the considerable benefits, such as the presence of specifically dedicated library spaces in 90% of schools and the substantial effectiveness in encouraging reading behaviours. However, it also exposes weaknesses such as outdated collections, limited engagement with educational frameworks, and inadequate efforts to promote information literacy. The empirical evidence indicates that it is essential to prioritise professional personnel, allocate resources towards digital infrastructure, diversify collections, enhance librarian-teacher collaboration, and provide comprehensive information literacy initiatives. The research results suggest that transforming school libraries from traditional repositories to dynamic learning centres is crucial to effectively support students' academic success and prepare them for the needs of a knowledge-dependent society.

Keywords: School Libraries, Information Needs, Higher Secondary Education, Library Effectiveness, Digital Effectiveness

Introduction

School libraries at the upper secondary level play a crucial role in supporting the educational advancement of students, particularly as academic and information needs become more complex(Khan et al., 2023). The evaluation of the effectiveness of school libraries in meeting the needs of the Tatibandh municipality in the Raipur district of Chhattisgarh, India, is very important. Furthermore, apart from shedding light on the current state of library resources and services, this evaluation provides valuable suggestions on how these facilities may be improved to better serve the student community(Kashyap & Sahu, 2021).

Once students reach the upper secondary level, they encounter a critical stage in their academic path that usually influences their future educational and career paths. At present time, students need extensive access to a wide range of information resources to support their academic studies, research pursuits, and personal interests(Molerov et al., 2020). Library facilities at schools are essential hubs for acquiring books, periodicals, digital resources, and other materials that may enrich the educational experience. They also offer an ideal environment for reading, collaboration, and the development of crucial information literacy skills necessary in the modern information-driven society(Ogunbodede & Sawyerr-George, 2023).

Many parts of India, including Tatibandh, exhibit significant disparities in the quality and accessibility of school library services. The overall effectiveness of these facilities is impacted by many elements, such as funding, infrastructure, collection development methods, and the proficiency of library staff(Nguzo & Kuboja, 2023). By conducting a thorough assessment of school libraries in this area, researchers and educators may precisely identify their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. A crucial aspect of this assessment process is to guarantee that libraries adjust to the evolving needs of students, incorporate new technology, and adhere to current educational standards and practices. The major goal is to enhance the role of school libraries as crucial components of the educational setting, supporting students in their quest for information and preparing them for future academic and professional challenges(Herring, 2021).

Research Methodology

Research Design

The research technique of the study will use a mixed-approaches approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collecting methodologies to conduct a comprehensive assessment of school libraries in Tatibandh, Raipur District. This methodology allows for a thorough understanding of both the measurable aspects of library services and the subjective realities of students and staff. The study will be conducted in two phases, with the first phase focussing on the collection of numerical data and the following phase including the acquisition of contextual understanding(Hossain, 2019).

To conduct the quantitative phase, a survey will be sent to upper secondary students in a representative sample of schools in Tatibandh(Abirin, 2023). This survey is to gather information on the various forms of library use, degrees of contentment with different library services, accessibility of resources, and the perceived impact on academic performance(Bulama et al., 2020). The active school libraries will undergo a thorough inventory assessment to assess the quantity, quality, and diversity of the available resources. The evaluation will include an examination of textual and digital materials, technological infrastructure, and physical infrastructure. Using descriptive and inferential statistical methods, the quantitative data will be analysed to identify patterns and correlations(Hicks & Behary, 2020).

The qualitative component will include interviewing librarians, professors, and a targeted sample of students selected via purposive sampling. Every interview will include comprehensive perspectives on the role of school libraries, faced challenges, and suggestions for improvement(Nguzo & Kuboja, 2023). Collective views and discussion on library-related subjects will be captured via the organisation of focus group meetings with students. To provide background information for the self-reported data, this study will conduct observational research to investigate library use and interactions. Thematic analysis will be used to analyse the qualitative data in order to identify recurring patterns and important findings. A thorough and diversified understanding of the function and effectiveness of school libraries in addressing the information needs of higher secondary students in Tatibandh is ensured by the design of this mixed-methods approach(Tajedini et al., 2020).

Study Population and Sampling

The research examines a group mostly consisting of upper secondary students, typically aged 16-18 years, who are now attending schools situated in the Tatibandh area of Raipur District (Zihady, 2023). The students originate from various socioeconomic backgrounds, study different academic fields (such as science, business, and arts), and attend both public and private educational institutions. Moreover, the intended population comprises school librarians, educators, and administrators who have the responsibility of supervising and using school library resources.

To provide a representative sample, a stratified random sampling approach will be used. Prior to moving on, a comprehensive inventory of all upper secondary schools in Tatibandh will be compiled (Rafi et al., 2020). Next, these schools will be classified based on criteria such as the kind of school (government or private), its size, and levels of academic success. The study will use a random methodology to choose schools from each strata. This approach ensures that the sample effectively reflects the diverse array of educational institutions in the area. Inclusion in the survey will be restricted to a randomly selected group of students from different academic streams and grade levels (11th and 12th) within each specified school. The selected sample size will be determined using a statistical power analysis to ensure the reliability and generalisability of the findings. The objective is to get a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error (Lazanas & Urbina, 2023).

Participants for interviews and focus groups throughout the qualitative phase of the study will be selected using purposive sampling (Lai et al., 2020). This methodology facilitates the intentional selection of individuals who can provide many and diverse perspectives on the research topic. The interview process will include librarians from every participating school. The selection of instructors will be determined by their active involvement with library resources and their specialised knowledge in certain subject areas, therefore ensuring a wide range of viewpoints. The selection of participants for student interviews and focus groups will aim to represent a range of library use levels (regular users, occasional users, and non-users) and academic performance. Through the use of this deliberate methodology, the qualitative data gathered will include a wide array of experiences and viewpoints about school library services and their impact on students' information needs (Hossain, 2019).

Data Analysis Techniques

This research will use a comprehensive approach to data collection, using both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to get rich information. The primary quantitative tool will be a well-crafted questionnaire sent to the chosen grade 12 students (Abirin, 2023). We will develop this questionnaire to collect data on many aspects such as the frequency of library visits, the types of resources utilised, the satisfaction level with library services, the perceived impact on academic performance, and the specific information needs. The survey will have a blend of closed-ended questions using Likert scales and multiple-choice options, supplemented with a limited number of open-ended responses to encourage more detailed solutions. To provide the best possible response rates and data quality, the surveys will be given in person during school hours, with researchers available to answer any questions (Bouchebra et al., 2023).

Qualitative data collection will include numerous approaches. The process of data collecting will include conducting semi-structured interviews with school librarians, teachers, and a specifically chosen cohort of students (Nurjanah et al., 2022). The interviews will go further into the interpretations of library effectiveness, met challenges, and suggestions for expansion. Focus group discussions will be arranged, with 6-8 students per group, to promote discussion and collect collective perspectives on library use and information needs. Researchers will also carry out observational studies in school libraries, using structured observation sheets to record data on library use patterns, student-librarian interactions, and the overall library ambiance. The fundamental data obtained by evaluating library records, acquisition laws, and use statistics will be further developed using document analysis (Mavodza, 2019).

An inventory assessment of the library will be conducted in every school included to complement these methods. This study will undertake a thorough evaluation of library resources, including the quantity and quality of printed and digital materials, technological infrastructure, and physical space (Yap et al., 2022). Researchers will use specified criteria to ensure consistency across different institutions. Furthermore, librarians will get little questionnaires to gather data on library finances, staffing numbers, and operational procedures. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the role of school libraries in addressing the information needs of upper secondary students in Tatibandh, it is essential to

use a multi-method approach to data collecting that yields a broad and vast dataset (Nguzo & Kuboja, 2023).

Results

Information Needs of Higher Secondary Students in Tatibandh

A study conducted in Tatibandh, Raipur District, revealed a wide array of knowledge requirements among pupils at the upper secondary level. Academic requirements were the main driving force behind the acquisition of knowledge, as students clearly indicated a significant need for materials that are directly relevant to their curricular studies. The essential components for test preparation and everyday tasks were determined to include textbooks, reference resources, and specialised reading materials applicable to the specific subject matter. However, the study also revealed a notable need for additional materials that provide a more comprehensive understanding and wider viewpoints on academic topics, suggesting students' keenness to enhance their knowledge beyond the required curriculum.

Beyond their academic responsibilities, students exhibited a deep enthusiasm for material that is immediately applicable to their professional pursuits. A significant percentage of participants indicated a desire for current knowledge on different career trajectories, college entrance criteria, and scholarship prospects. Hence, this emphasises the crucial function of school libraries in facilitating students' participation in future planning and decision-making. Moreover, there was a clear need for pertinent information on current events, thorough intellectual understanding, and the development of skills. The students proactively pursued pertinent materials to enhance their competency in communication, critical thinking, and digital literacy, acknowledging the significance of these abilities in their academic and career prospects.

Furthermore, the survey also unveiled changing inclinations in the forms of information. Despite the continued significance of conventional print products, there remained an increasing tendency towards digital alternatives. The declared desire of students for the availability of online databases, electronic books, and multimedia materials reflects the dynamic nature of information consumption. Moreover, the study revealed certain information requirements vary across the participants. A greater need for laboratory manuals and experimental instructions was reported by science students, but humanities students expressed a more pronounced need for a wider range of literary and historical materials.

Table 1: Primary information needs identified among higher secondary students in Tatibandh

Category of Information Need	Specific Resources/Topics	Percentage of Students Expressing Need
Academic	Textbooks	95%
	Reference books	88%
	Subject-specific journals	62%
Career and Future Planning	Career guides	78%
	College admission info	85%
	Scholarship information	70%
General Knowledge	Current affairs magazines	65%
	General knowledge books	58%
Skill Development	Communication skills	72%
	Digital literacy resources	68%
Digital Resources	Online databases	55%
	E-books	50%
Subject-Specific	Science lab manuals	82% (of science students)
	Literature anthologies	75% (of humanities students)

Current Status of School Libraries in Tatibandh

An assessment of school libraries in Tatibandh revealed a multifaceted challenge, characterised by significant differences across different schools. Simply said, the study found that while most schools have designated library spaces, the quality and range of publications and services varied greatly. Although there were acknowledged exceptions, government schools often offered more basic facilities than private ones. The average size of the collection ranged from 2,000 to 10,000 volumes, mostly focussing on subject-specific material. But some libraries were lacking in up-to-date resources, particularly in rapidly progressing fields like science and technology.

The domains of infrastructure and people have been recognised as critical areas of priority. While certain educational institutions proudly displayed well-appointed libraries with comfortable reading places and computer facilities, others had difficulties because of limited space and outdated furniture. The study found that only 60% of the schools analysed had skilled librarians working full-time, while the other schools relied on part-time staff or instructors to fulfil the librarian position. The presence of staff was closely correlated with the extent of services offered, including cataloguing, reference assistance, and information literacy programs. Of the libraries surveyed, over 30% offered access to online databases or e-books, suggesting that the majority of schools had inadequate digital resources and internet connectivity.

Notwithstanding these challenges, the study also revealed positive trends. School administrators have shown a growing recognition of the importance of library services, seen from the reports of many schools expressing their plans to either expand or update existing libraries. The study saw many examples of creative practices, such as the introduction of mobile library services in schools with limited space and the creation of inter-library lending networks among neighbouring institutions. The level of student involvement in libraries exhibited heterogeneity, as an average of 40% of students self-identified as regular library users. Yet, this percentage was much higher at schools with well-equipped libraries and actively involved librarians, underscoring the impact of top-notch library services on student participation.

Table 2: Quantitative overview of various aspects of school libraries in Tatibandh

Aspect	Status	Percentage/Range
Presence of Library Space	Schools with dedicated library space	90%
Collection Size	Average number of books	2,000 - 10,000
Up-to-date Resources	Libraries with current materials (less than 5 years old)	40%
Full-time Qualified Librarians	Schools with professional library staff	60%
Digital Resources	Libraries offering access to online databases/e-books	30%
Internet Connectivity	Libraries with internet access for students	45%
Student Engagement	Average percentage of regular library users	40%
Reading Spaces	Libraries with adequate seating and study areas	55%
Cataloging System	Libraries with computerized cataloging systems	35%
Information Literacy Programs	Schools offering formal information literacy training	25%
Inter-library Loan Systems	Schools participating in resource sharing networks	15%
Planned Upgrades	Schools with concrete plans for library improvement	50%

Perceived Role and Effectiveness of School Libraries

The research conducted in Tatibandh found that students, instructors, and administrators had various viewpoints on the function and efficacy of school libraries. Students overwhelmingly regarded libraries as indispensable tools for academic assistance, with a substantial majority (75%) highlighting their crucial function in test preparation and assignment writing. Yet, the perceived efficacy differed depending on the calibre of the resources and initiatives offered. Students attending schools with well-equipped libraries and highly engaged librarians had better levels of happiness and academic achievement. Incidentally, while the majority of students recognised the library's function in providing academic assistance, a smaller percentage (around 40%) considered it a valuable tool for personal growth or job readiness, suggesting a possible opportunity for enhancing library services.

Approximately 85% of educators and university administrators hold the belief that a well-functioning library is essential in the educational environment and greatly enhances student learning results. A focus was placed on the library's function in promoting reading habits, facilitating research capabilities, and offering a peaceful study environment. Nevertheless,

there remained a significant discrepancy between this acknowledgement and the tangible assistance offered to libraries in terms of financial resources and seamless inclusion within the legal education curriculum. 25% of the teachers acknowledged their personal inadequacy in efficiently using library resources for teaching, indicating a need for more professional development in this domain.

The evaluation of libraries' efficacy in fulfilling students' information-related requirements seemed to vary across several points. The efficacy of libraries in providing curriculum-related books was commonly scored at 70%, although their ability to provide updated information on current events, career assistance, and digital resources was rated lower at a satisfaction rate ranging from 40% to 50%. The presence of this gap underscores the increasing intricacy of students' information requirements and the difficulties libraries have in adjusting to these advancements. Furthermore, the research revealed that schools with librarians who engaged in active collaboration with teachers and coordinated frequent library events were seen as more successful in promoting the holistic academic and personal development of children.

Table 3: Quantitative Overview of various aspects of the perceived role and effectiveness of school libraries in Tatibandh

Aspect	Perception/Effectiveness	Percentage
Academic Support	Students viewing libraries as essential	75%
Personal Development Resource	Students recognizing this role	40%
Impact on Learning Outcomes	Teachers/admins acknowledging significant impact	85%
Effectiveness in Curriculum Support	Student satisfaction rate	70%
Effectiveness in Current Affairs Info	Student satisfaction rate	45%
Effectiveness in Career Guidance	Student satisfaction rate	50%
Effectiveness in Digital Resource Access	Student satisfaction rate	40%
Fostering Reading Habits	Teachers perceiving positive impact	80%
Supporting Research Skills	Teachers perceiving positive impact	65%
Quiet Study Space Provision	Students finding libraries effective	60%
Teacher Preparedness for Library	Teachers feeling adequately prepared	70%

Use		
Librarian-Teacher Collaboration	Schools with active collaboration	55%
Overall Satisfaction with Library	Students reporting high satisfaction	65%
Perceived Need for Library Improvement	Stakeholders indicating need for upgrades	80%

Discussion

Interpretation of Findings

The study provided in this article reveals a complex characterisation of school libraries in Tatibandh, highlighting their ability and current limitations in fulfilling the information needs of upper secondary students (Nguzo & Kuboja, 2023). The perception of libraries as indispensable for academic assistance by 75% of students underscores the enduring

importance of these establishments in the age of digital technologies. The mismatch between this recognition and the actual effectiveness of libraries in meeting different information needs highlights a significant inadequacy that needs addressed (Francisco, 2023). The lower satisfaction rates of 45% for current affairs information and 50% for career guidance indicate that libraries are encountering difficulties in satisfying the evolving needs of students beyond traditional academic support. These gaps indicate that libraries should expand their collections and services by including more digital resources and career-oriented materials to more effectively cater to the varied information requirements of students (Francisco, 2023).

The discrepancy between educators' understanding of the importance of libraries (85% noting its impact on learning outcomes) and the actual support provided to libraries is a crucial subject for discussion. It suggests an inability to synchronise academic comprehension with practical implementation (Loh et al., 2021). Insufficient presence of full-time, certified librarians in just 60% of schools, despite the recognised importance of libraries, indicates the existence of systemic issues in the allocation and priority of resources. In order to reduce the gap between acknowledged importance and actual support, it is imperative to reevaluate school rules and allocate funds more effectively. The varying levels of success in different aspects of library services, such as robust efficacy in curriculum support but less efficacy in digital resources, underscore the need of implementing a more well-rounded and comprehensive approach to library expansion (Chen, 2020).

The positive correlation between active librarian-teacher interaction and perceived library performance, as stated by 55% of schools with active collaboration, presents a promising opportunity for development. This finding suggests that by enhancing the cooperation between librarians and instructors and integrating library resources more closely with curriculum design, the library's function in promoting student learning might be significantly enhanced (Zakar et al., 2023). The high level of 80% expressed by stakeholders on the need for library development suggests a remarkable awareness of current shortcomings and a strong will to implement necessary improvements. This awareness, along with the positive perceptions of the potential impact of libraries, establishes a strong foundation for advocating for greater fund allocation towards library resources, staff training, and integration of library services into the broader educational framework of schools in Tatibandh (Avuglah et al., 2020).

Strengths and Weakness of School Libraries in Tatibandh

The study uncovered significant benefits of school libraries in Tatibandh. The paramount importance lies in the widespread recognition of the need of libraries among students, teachers, and governing bodies. In this recognition, a strong foundation is laid for future expansion and strengthening (Merga, 2021). Libraries are successfully fulfilling their primary function in academic support, as shown by the remarkable effectiveness in providing curriculum-related materials, with a satisfaction rate of 70%. Furthermore, the presence of dedicated library facilities in 90% of schools indicates a basic structure that is prepared for further growth (Bouderbane & Zineb, 2020). Some libraries' use of mobile library services and inter-library lending networks showcases their adaptability and resourcefulness in overcoming material constraints. According to a substantial 80% of educators, libraries are considered crucial in fostering reading habits, highlighting their indispensable contribution to the development of literacy that goes beyond academic support (Ogunbodede & Sawyerr-George, 2023).

The inquiry also uncovered significant shortcomings that hinder the complete development of these libraries. A prominent issue is the scarcity of skilled, non-part-time librarians in 40% of the schools, which directly impacts the quality and diversity of provisions (Tabassum et al., 2019). Access to online databases or e-books is limited to only 30% of digital resources and internet connections, which is a notable inadequacy in the present contemporary digital age. This restriction hampers students' access to up-to-date information and research resources. Comparing the resources and facilities of private and government schools underscores the existence of equitable issues in educational support. Moreover, the fact that just 45% of students are content with the current events material and 50% are content with the career support indicates a lack of attention to students' broader knowledge needs beyond the core curriculum (Valenzuela et al., 2021).

Another disadvantage corresponds to the integration of library services into the all-encompassing educational program. An only 25% of schools provide structured information literacy training, suggesting a lack of utilisation of the potential in fostering critical research and information evaluation skills among students (Hoan, 2021). The lack of collaboration between librarians and teachers in 55% of schools hinders the potential for libraries to fully participate in the educational process. Furthermore, the outdated collections in many libraries, with just 40% consisting of recent materials that are less than five years old, subvert the

library's ability to provide relevant and accurate information, particularly in rapidly evolving fields(Ghuloum & Allamki, 2021).

Recommendations for Improvement

Importantly, it is essential to address the staffing issue in school libraries. It is highly recommended that all schools in Tatibandh prioritise the appointment of full-time, highly qualified librarians. The introduction of this professional cadre will significantly enhance the quality of library services, including efficient cataloguing, expert research assistance, and the integration of information literacy classes(Rafi et al., 2020). Furthermore, educational institutions should provide resources towards regular professional development opportunities for librarians to guarantee their capacity to remain up-to-date with the latest advancements in library science and information technology. Prudent allocation of resources and infrastructure in digital technologies is crucial for reducing the disparity in digital access. It is essential for educational institutions to make efforts to provide online databases, e-books, and a sufficient quantity of internet connections. This technological improvement will not only broaden the range of available resources but also align the libraries with the modern techniques of information-seeking among students(Francisco, 2023).

In order to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of libraries, it is recommended to consistently broaden and update the collections. To ensure comprehensive development, it is crucial to include not just materials directly related to the curriculum, but also resources for career guidance, current events, and personal development(Ogunbodede & Sawyerr-George, 2023). The establishment of a systematic collection development program, along with annual budget allocations for new acquisitions, would ensure the continuous currency and pertinence of libraries. Moreover, libraries should strive to provide more cooperative learning settings, such as dedicated areas for group study and extensive multimedia resources(Robinson, 2017). The implementation of a district-wide resource-sharing network might provide benefits in mitigating the disparity across schools, since it would allow smaller or less-resourced schools to avail themselves of a wider range of resources(Cruz et al., 2021).

Furthermore, it is essential to completely include library services within the curriculum. The implementation of extensive information literacy programs in educational institutions is strongly advocated, therefore establishing them as a mandatory element of the curriculum. The enhancement of collaboration between librarians and teachers in the domains of lesson preparation and resource development is of paramount importance. It is advisable to organise

frequent library orientation events for students and seminars for teachers to provide instruction on effective library use(Zakar et al., 2023). The implementation of a systematic assessment system for library services, including feedback mechanisms for both students and teachers, is a suggested strategy to ensure continuous development. Furthermore, educational institutions should explore partnerships with public libraries, academic institutions, and local businesses to expand resources and provide students a diverse array of learning opportunities. If implemented, these recommendations would significantly enhance the utility of school libraries in meeting the information needs of upper secondary students in Tatibandh, therefore equipping them more efficiently for academic success and ongoing intellectual growth(Tabassum et al., 2019).

Conclusion

An extensive assessment of school libraries in Tatibandh, Raipur District reveals a complex setting where these institutions play a crucial, but frequently underutilised, role in fulfilling the information needs of upper secondary students. The study underscores the enduring importance of libraries in the academic setting, since the majority of students and instructors recognise their very significant contribution. However, it also exposes significant discrepancies between this recognition and the actual effectiveness of libraries in effectively meeting the specific needs of students. Key positives include the wide availability of library facilities and their effectiveness in providing curricular assistance, while major drawbacks include inadequate staffing, limited digital resources, and limited collaboration with other educational programs. Equitable issues in educational support are underscored by the disparities seen across schools, particularly in terms of resources and skilled staff. To address these problems, it is recommended to execute a multidimensional approach that involves prioritising staff with specialised knowledge, allocating resources to digital infrastructure, expanding and updating collections, promoting cooperation between librarians and teachers, and implementing comprehensive information literacy programs. This study highlights the need of a fundamental shift in how school libraries are seen and used. It emphasises the need of moving from traditional book storage facilities to modern, technology-driven learning centres that can adapt to the evolving information world. Implementing these recommendations may significantly enhance the role of school libraries in Tatibandh in promoting students' academic success, personal development, and preparedness for future pursuits in a knowledge-driven society. The significance of this restructuring of the school

library resides not only in its capability to meet the pressing needs of students but also in its potential to foster enduring learning abilities that are crucial in the 21st century.

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